

Determination of isoniazid using mercury(II) ion selective membrane electrode

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Abstract : A Hg^{II} ion selective membrane electrode was fabricated using mercury-8-hydroxyquinolate as an electroactive material and PVC as an inert binder. The electrode gave linear response in the concentration range 1×10^{-1} – 1×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ of Hg^{II} ions. The working pH range was 3–10 and the response time was 20 s. The electrode was selective for Hg^{II} ions in the presence of number of cations such as Ba^{II}, Ca^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II}. In the present work, the isoniazid ammonium vanadate complex was also investigated using spectrophotometry so that these determinations could be compared with the values obtained from electrochemical sensor.

Keywords : Hg^{II}, isoniazid, determination, electrode.

Introduction

Isoniazid is an antibacterial drug. It is given for all forms of tuberculosis including those associated with HIV infections. This drug was found to be very active and this was introduced under the generic name called isoniazid (INH). Chemically this drug is the hydrazide of isonicotinic acid (pyridine-4-carboxylic acid). Isoniazid rapidly eliminates organisms which are actively multiplying in areas with high oxygen tensions. It is rated highly effective in early bacterial activity and in prevention of resistance, therefore, it finds use in the primary treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis. It is also found to be effective in extra pulmonary lesions. Isoniazid is also successfully employed in the treatment of tuberculosis of skin.

Various classical as well as physicochemical methods have been used for the determination of this compound in pharmaceutical preparations. A number of scientist used titrimetric method for the determination of isoniazid¹⁻⁵. Andras⁶, Issopoulos⁷⁻¹⁰ and Mohfouz *et al.*¹¹ carried out colorimetric determination of isoniazid and its pharmaceutical formulations. Isoniazid can also be determined spectrophotometrically using different oxidants¹²⁻²⁰. Recently several new HPLC based methods have been developed for the determination of isoniazid²¹⁻²³.

The increasing demand for chemical surveillance in

environmental protection, medicine and many industrial processes has created the need for sensors with features, such as high selectivity, sensitivity, reliability and sturdiness. These demands can often be satisfied by ion selective electrodes (ISES), which are commonly used owing to their simplicity, lower cost and fast provision for analytical results.

A number of potentiometric methods have been developed for the determination of isoniazid²¹⁻²⁶. Koupperis *et al.*²⁷ carried out indirect potentiometric procedures with chloramine-T. Graphite membrane electrode was developed by Paster and co-workers²⁸. Another electrodes which were used for the determination of isoniazid includes Cu^{II} selective electrode, iodide selective electrode, platinum wire electrode, fluoride and silver selective electrode²⁹⁻³³. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to determine isoniazid using a novel Hg^{II} membrane ion selective electrode. The electrode was fabricated for the first time using Hg^{II} 8-hydroxyquinolate complex as an electroactive material. This was then used for potentiometric determination of isoniazid in pure and in pharmaceutical samples.

The isoniazid ammonium vanadate complex was also investigated using spectrophotometry and applied for the determination of isoniazid present in pharmaceutical

sample, so that these determinations could be compared with the values obtained from electrochemical sensor.

Results and discussion

Electrometric technique :

After conditioning the electrode (the electrode was dipped in 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ solution of HgCl₂ for 24 h before use), the electrode potentials for a series of standard solutions in the concentration range 1.0×10^{-1} to 1.0×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³ were measured with the help of Hg^{II} membrane ion selective electrode and standard calomel electrode as reference electrode. A linear response was observed for Hg^{II} concentration down to 1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. The slope was found to be 34 mV per decade change in Hg^{II} ion concentration.

In order to find out the response time of the electrode, the electrode was first dipped in 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ solution of the Hg^{II} ion and suddenly the concentration of solution was changed to 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³. The values of potential changes were noted at every 5 s. A constant potential was obtained after 20 s.

To study the effect of pH, the pH of the 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ HgCl₂ solution was varied by the addition of dilute solution of NaOH or HCl, it was found that the potential remain unchanged within the pH range 3 to 10 (working range).

The selectivity coefficients for different cations Hg^{II} ion were determined by mixed solution method³⁴. For this the concentration of Hg^{II} ion was varied while the concentration of interfering ion was kept constant at 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³.

The electrode is selective in the presence of several closely associated metals (Table 1).

Table 1. Electrode selectivity coefficients, determined by mixed solution method

Cations (M)	Ba ^{II}	Ca ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Pb ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Mn ^{II}
Selectivity coefficient	0.19	0.19	0.04	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.04	0.04

The life time of the electrode was found to be 36 weeks of its fabrication.

Application :

The electrode was used as an indicator electrode in the determination of isoniazid in pure form and in pharmaceutical preparations.

Principle :

In this method the isoniazid is treated with alcoholic iodine solution containing sodium bicarbonate (pH 8.8). The isoniazid is oxidized to isonicotinic acid and equivalent amount of iodide is produced which is determined by titration against standard silver nitrate solution using Hg^{II} selective membrane electrode as an indicator electrode.

Analysis of pure isoniazid :

An aliquot (25 mL) containing 25 mg of isoniazid was taken from the stock solution and 10.0 mL of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ sodium bicarbonate (pH 8.8) was added. After that a freshly prepared 0.1 mol dm⁻³ ethanolic iodine was added dropwise until yellow colour of iodine persisted. The pH of this solution was reduced to 3.0 with 0.1 mol dm⁻³ nitric acid and then 10.0 mL of potassium hydrogen phthalate-nitrate buffer (pH 3.0) was added and the solution was diluted to 50 mL with water after that it was titrated against 0.01 mol dm⁻³ AgNO₃ using Hg^{II} membrane ion selective electrode as an indicator electrode and a calomel electrode as a reference electrode. After each addition potential was recorded.

Analysis of pharmaceutical preparation of isoniazid :

20 Tablets of isoniazid SOLONOX – Macleods Pharmaceutical Ltd. were taken and crushed to fine powder. An appropriate amount of powdered sample equivalent to 100 mg was dissolved in 50 mL of distilled water and filtered off using Whatman filter paper No. 42 and washed several times with water. The combined filtrate and washings was diluted to 100 mL. Rest of the procedure was same as in case of pure form. After each addition potential was recorded. The value of analyte was found out from the titration curve. For pure as well as pharmaceutical samples three different titrations was performed with different volume of aliquot. The results of determination of isoniazid in pure form and pharmaceutical preparation in different samples are summarized in the Table 2.

Spectrophotometric technique :

Determination of wavelength of maximum absorption :

To determine the wave length of maximum absorption a solution was prepared mixing 5 mL of 1 mg/mL of isoniazid solution, 3 mL of 1.5×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ of ammonium vanadate and 2 mL of 0.2% metol solution. To this 10 mL potassium hydrogen phthalate-hydrochloric

Table 2. Results of determination of isoniazid in pure form and in pharmaceutical preparation

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquot taken (mL)	Amount (mg)
1.	Isoniazid (pure)	20	19.87
		25	24.82
		30	29.88
2.	SOLONOX Tab. (Macleods Pharm. Ltd.)	20	19.01
		25	24.04
		30	29.17

ric acid buffer (pH 2.2) was also added and diluted to 25 mL. Recording of absorption spectrum shows the wave length of maximum absorption is 605 nm.

A series of solutions were prepared with varying amounts of isoniazid but fixed concentrations of ammonium vanadate and metol solutions. 10 mL of potassium hydrogen phthalate-hydrochloric acid buffer (pH 2.2) was added to each solution. After development of colour, the absorbance of each solution was measured at 605 nm against a blank treated similarly. The absorbance values were plotted against concentration of isoniazid and it was observed that Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 10–100 µg/mL. The Sandell's sensitivity was also determined (0.1144 µg cm⁻²).

The sample solutions were treated in similar fashion and absorbance of each solution was measured. From calibration curve isoniazid content in SOLONOX tablets was evaluated. From a set of five such measurements the average value of pharmaceutical samples was evaluated which is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Estimation of isoniazid in SOLONOX tablets

Sample	Aliquot taken (mL)	Absorbance (A)	Amount obtained (mg)	Observed value (mg)	
				Average ^a	Standard deviation
C1	1.0	0.342	24.07	24.67	0.03
C2	1.2	0.415	24.63		
C3	1.4	0.485	24.66		
C4	1.6	0.555	24.68		
C5	1.8	0.615	24.70		

^aAverage of 5 determinations.

The determination of isoniazid content from pharmaceutical preparations by electrochemical method as well as spectrophotometric method (Table 4) for a given amount shows fairly good agreement in the values.

Table 4. Comparison of results obtained by potentiometry and by spectrophotometry for isoniazid pharmaceutical sample

Sample	Amount present (mg)	Amount obtained (mg)		
		Electrode	Spectro-photometry	S.D
SOLONOX Tab. (Macleods Pharm. Ltd.)	25	24.54	24.66	0.03

Experimental

Reagents :

All the chemicals used were of A.R. or G.R. grades of E. Merck, B.D.H. and Qualigens, respectively. Isoniazid [Unicare Remedies (Pvt.) Ltd., Vadodara]. The pharmaceutical preparation of isoniazid (SOLONOX – Macleods Pharm. Ltd.). Ion free double distilled water was used throughout the experiment.

Instruments :

A Philips pH/mV meter (Model 9405m) with a silver-silver chloride electrode as a reference electrode was used for the measurement of electrode potential. A digital pH meter (Century CP 901) with combined electrode was used for pH measurements. Spectrophotometric data were obtained using a digital UV-Visible spectrophotometer (SICO Feedback) with 10 mm quartz cuvettes. All measurements were carried out at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C).

Preparation of electroactive material and membrane :

The Hg^{II} 8-hydroxyquinolate precipitate was used as an electroactive material for preparation of the membrane.

200 mg of this substance was mixed with PVC (100 mg) in 6 mL tetrahydrofuran (THF) and finally mixed with 2 drops of dioctylphthalate. Resulting solution was cast into a slide glass and left for slow evaporation to get a thin membrane. A portion of the membrane of appropriate size was cut from the master membrane and was mounted at the lower end of the glasstube (diameter 1 cm and length 15 cm) and it was dried for 24 h. The tube was filled with 0.01 mol dm⁻³ metal solution and kept immersed in metal solution of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ for one week. The internal reference electrode was Ag-AgCl and external reference electrode was calomel electrode.

The entire electrode system for the measurement can be represented as

Internal reference electrode	Internal reference solution	Hg ^{II} ion selective membrane	Sample solution	External reference electrode (SCE)
Ag-AgCl	(0.01 mol dm ⁻³ HgCl ₂)			

Before making measurements the electrode assembly was dipped in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ solution of HgCl₂ for 24 h.

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